

Acknowledgements

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Reference

1. MAXWELL. *Organic Synthesis*, 1943, 23, 30.

Phase Studies in the System $Sb_x Sm_{(1-x)} NbO_4$

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VARIOUS workers¹⁻³ have studied the X-ray diffraction patterns of the stibio-columbite and tried to correlate its structure with the rare-earth columbites. However the present system is not studied by any worker. We studied this system in order to investigate the structural correlation of samario-columbite and stibio-columbite; and to justify the symmetry of samario-columbite.

Spectrochemically pure samples of the component oxides were mixed according to suitable proportions, grinded well and thoroughly mixed by a ball-mill

for two hours using acetone as mixer. The samples were fired in various temperature ranges, at 300° for six hours, 800° for six hours, 1100° for two hours, 1250° for two hours and finally quenched to room temperature in air. The powder was analysed by a standard diffractometer. The diffractometer charts were used to calculate the lattice parameters and to detect the developed phases.

The results are given in the Table 1. It is observed that on introduction of 40% Sm^{3+} ions into the stibio-columbite lattice replacing Sb^{3+} ions in A sites, the samario-columbite phase developed with very faint peaks. On further substitution the intensity of the peaks due to samario-columbite phase increased progressively until the last compound. Various workers⁴⁻⁶ studied the X-ray diffraction patterns of synthetic samario-columbite, but the reported symmetries were inconsistent. We indexed the pattern on the basis of orthorhombic symmetry with the lattice parameters

$$a = 4.45. \quad b = 12.89 \text{ and } c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$$

The X-ray data of samario-columbite is given in the Table 2.

It is observed that samario-columbite is iso-structural with stibio-columbite, having the structure consisting of samarium atoms surrounded by oxygen octahedra and these octahedra share two edges with one another forming chains parallel to C_0 axis. Each niobium atom is surrounded by a tetrahedron of oxygen atoms belonging to three octahedral units

TABLE 1—The system $Sb_x Sm_{(1-x)} NbO_4$

No.	Composition	Molecular weight	Colour	Phases present
W ₁	$Sb_{0.9} Sm_{0.2} NbO_4$	284.38	Yellow	Stibio-columbite $a = 4.98, b = 12.56, c = 5.52 \text{ \AA}$
W ₂	$Sb_{0.8} Sm_{0.4} NbO_4$	290.10	Pale-yellow	Stibio-columbite + Samario-columbite $a = 5.10, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$
W ₃	$Sb_{0.4} Sm_{0.7} NbO_4$	295.51	Pale-yellow	Stibio-columbite + Samario columbite $a = 5.22, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$
W ₄	$Sb_{0.2} Sm_{0.8} NbO_4$	301.04	Yellow-white	Stibio-columbite + Samario-columbite $a = 5.34, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$
W ₅	$Sm NbO_4$	307.26	Yellowish white	Samario-columbite $a = 4.45, b = 12.89, c = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$

TABLE 2—Mo K_{α} RADIATION

X-ray data of Sm NbO ₄		
dm Å	I/I ₀	hkl
4.624	20	110
3.855	10	101
3.449	15	111
3.193	100	121
3.002	90	040
2.760	20	002
2.689	20	012
2.462	10	220
2.377	15	211
2.272	10	221
2.195	10	151
2.046	15	231, 240
1.932	30	212
1.878	30	161
1.778	20	232
1.654	30	123
1.589	30	170, 133
1.499	15	080
1.353	10	004
1.336	10	024
1.304	20	124

of oxygen atoms, and these tetrahedra run through-out; and can be considered as the binding unit for the entire structural system.

References

1. R. M. THOMPSON, Univ. British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada, 1959. A.S.T.M. index.
2. R. S. ROTH and J. L. WARING, *Amer. Mineralogist*, 1963, 48, 1348.
3. A. C. SKAPSKI, (Univ. Stockholm) *Chem. Commun. England*, 1965, 23, 611.
4. A. I. KOMKOV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. SSSR*, 1959, 126, 853.
5. A. I. KOMKOV, *Materialy Vsesoyuz. Nauz—Issledovatel. Geol. Inst.*, 1959, 26, 73.
6. H. P. ROOKSBY and E. A. D. WHITE, *Wembley Eng. Acta. Cryst.*, 1963, 16(a), 888.

Aromatic amines as corrosion inhibitor for 63/37 brass in acetic acid solutions

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ALIPHATIC amines, heterocyclic amines and aromatic amines have been extensively studied as corrosion inhibitors of metals and alloys in various media¹⁻⁶. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to evaluate the inhibitive efficiency of aniline and the effect of some groups in the benzene ring of aniline. Following substances were studied: *o*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and phenetidine.

Experimental

Brass sheets (63/37) were cold rolled and annealed at 550°. It has the following composition

Cu-63.2, Zn-36.6, Sn-0.07 and Pb-0.01%.

Preparation, corrosion testing and cleaning of specimens were same as described before⁷. Each specimen of the size 3×6 cm (26 S.W.G.) was fully immersed in 260 ml. of the solution. All experiments were carried out at 32°-5°. Experiments were performed in 0.5 *N* acetic acid solution, using various concentrations of the inhibitors.

The duration for exposure was 10 days. Results are represented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The results reveal that *o*-toluidine is a very poor inhibitor, while *o*-phenetidine is an excellent inhibitor. The order of increase in inhibitive power is

p-Anisidine < Aniline < *o*-Toluidine < *o*-phenetidine

According to Mann when metal is introduced into an electrolyte, it becomes -ve charged. Helmholtz's double layer is formed on the surface, the +ve ions of the metal tending to go into solution. H⁺ in the solution can replace the metal ions and ultimately get discharged as hydrogen gas. If the inhibitors form an ionizable salt with the metal in the corrosive acid, there will be positive inhibitor ions which may now replace the +ve metal ions of the double layer. Mann assumed that the salt of an amine will be ionized, the positive charge being concentrated on nitrogen. Thus the inhibitor ion is attracted to the cathodic areas of the metal through nitrogen⁸.

Further, nitrogen in NH₂ and oxygen in -OC₂H₅ and -OCH₃ contain respectively one and two lone pairs of electrons. The lone pair electrons makes such atoms adsorbable at suitable sites over the metal surface.